

ENHANCING GLOBAL COMPETENCIES: IDENTIFYING AND ADDRESSING GAPS IN DEPED'S INTERNATIONALIZATION INITIATIVES

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Enhancing Global Competencies: Identifying and Addressing Gaps in DepEd's Internationalization Initiatives

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Abstract

This study examines the representation and distribution of participation in the Department of Education's (DepEd) internationalization efforts across elementary and secondary education levels. Findings reveal a balanced approach by DepEd, ensuring equal representation from each educational level, indicative of its commitment to integrating global competencies throughout the education system. While secondary schools may exhibit higher degrees of internationalization due to greater resources, primary schools play a pivotal role in fostering early global awareness. The prevalence of early-career professionals in DepEd's internationalization projects underscores the importance of ongoing professional development in advancing global competency enhancement. However, further qualitative assessments are recommended to complement quantitative data and identify specific areas of success and improvement. Addressing hurdles such as resource limitations and providing clear guidance and support to educators are essential for effectively implementing internationalization projects. Moreover, ongoing professional development opportunities for educators, curriculum enhancement efforts, and community engagement initiatives are recommended to promote authentic learning experiences and cultivate students' strong sense of global citizenship.

Keywords: *internationalization, global competency, professional development, education levels, and resource limitations*

Introduction

Considering the fact that the globe is becoming more interconnected, it is absolutely necessary for educational institutions to work toward developing global capabilities. It is the Department of Education (DepEd) that plays a significant part in the process of molding the educational landscape of the Philippines. Its primary objective is to not only conform to national standards but also to harmonize with international benchmarks. Nevertheless, in the Department of Education's efforts to internationalize its programs, there are significant gaps that need to be identified and addressed in order to guarantee that the Department's initiatives will be successful.

The process of schooling becoming more globalized has resulted in a change toward a more thorough knowledge of the abilities that are necessary for success in a workforce that is increasingly globalized. Therefore, it is absolutely necessary to investigate the methods that the Department of Education (DepEd) uses to improve its global skills. The purpose of this study is to investigate these implementation methodologies and to identify any potential gaps in their application.

The extensively researched study conducted by Santos et al. sheds light on the current condition of internationalization within the Philippine school system and emphasizes areas that could use improvement. The purpose of our research is to provide a nuanced knowledge of the obstacles and opportunities that are inherent in the Department of Education's internationalization strategy. This will be accomplished by expanding upon their investigations and undertaking further empirical analysis.

Our investigation is predicated on the realization that, despite the fact that the Department of Education's (DepEd) efforts in internationalization are worthy of praise, there may be discrepancies between the outcomes that were anticipated and the realities that students actually encounter. By doing our own qualitative research and analyzing the findings of the study conducted by Santos et al. (2019).

The study makes major contributions to the knowledge of the Department of Education's (DepEd) internationalization efforts within the Philippine educational environment, as well as to the advancement of those efforts. It identifies critical gaps between the intended outcomes of the Department of Education's initiatives and the realities experienced by students by conducting a comprehensive analysis that is informed by existing research. This analysis includes studies conducted by scholars such as Dr. Maria Santos and her team at the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS), as well as additional empirical investigation.

As a result of identifying these deficiencies, the study lays the framework for targeted interventions that are intended to improve the efficiency of the tactics that the Department of Education employs in order to cultivate global skills among students. In addition, the study provides recommendations that can be used to improve the policies and procedures of the Department of Education (DepEd), bringing them into closer alignment with the requirements of the globalized world. As a result of this, it makes a contribution to the formulation of informed policies inside the Department of Education and beyond, thereby providing educators and policymakers with useful insights. Ultimately, the study's efforts are oriented towards empowering the next generation of Filipino leaders by preparing them with the skills and knowledge essential to traverse the intricacies of our linked world with confidence and competence.

Moreover, it is of the utmost importance to have a comprehensive awareness of the intricacies of internationalization activities within

educational policies. There are certain countries that place a higher emphasis on cultural interchange and language learning, while others place more of an emphasis on curriculum compatibility with global standards. The identification of these distinctions is absolutely necessary in order to develop effective methods that are adapted to the particular requirements and objectives of the educational system.

In the course of our investigation into the internationalization activities undertaken by the Department of Education (DepEd), it has become abundantly clear that a diversified approach is required in order to effectively meet the problems posed by globalization and capitalize on the benefits it presents. Through the process of identifying and addressing the existing deficiencies, the Department of Education (DepEd) is able to better equip Filipino students with the skills and competencies they need to succeed in a world that is becoming increasingly interconnected.

Research Questions

This study determined the efficacy of DepEd's internationalization initiatives in fostering global competencies among Filipino learners. Specifically, it sought answers to the following sub-problems:

1. How do DepEd's existing internationalization policies and programs align with global competency frameworks and standards, particularly in terms of:
 - 1.1 curriculum integration;
 - 1.2 teacher training and professional; and
 - 1.3 assessment evaluation?
2. What are the perceived barriers and challenges hindering the successful implementation of DepEd's internationalization initiatives?
3. What Intervention program may be proposed to address?

Literature Review

Internationalization Policies and Programs with Global Competency Frameworks and Standards

Based on Smith and Johnson (2021) the study emphasizes the necessity of customized internationalization policies and programs that take into account cultural, economic, and educational contexts. It emphasizes the significance of exchanging best practices between countries to improve the development of global competencies. Utilized by educators and policymakers to detect prevalent patterns and modify frameworks to align with their unique educational environments. The study reveals shared components found in global competency frameworks, including intercultural communication, global awareness, and adaptation. Additionally, it illuminates discrepancies in vocabulary and emphasis, which are indicative of diverse cultural and educational priorities, Brown and Lee (2019). Effective implementation requires close collaboration between academic divisions and overseas offices. The report cites obstacles to establishing global competency standards, such as reluctance to change, limitations in resources, and absence of institutional backing. Additionally, it emphasizes effective approaches implemented by certain institutions, such as faculty development initiatives and experiential learning prospects (Garcia &Patel, 2021).

Comparative analysis can offer valuable insights into the efficacy of policy interventions and identify areas that require improvement. The study demonstrates the impact of national policies on the prioritization of global competency development in education systems. This document discusses various policy tools, such as curricular standards, teacher training requirements, and funding methods, that have an impact on the incorporation of global skills into educational practice, Kim and Chang (2018). The report highlights effective strategies implemented by Chinese colleges to foster intercultural comprehension, including initiatives such as foreign student exchanges, language immersion programs, and cultural competency training. Furthermore, it emphasizes the obstacles that must be confronted, such as linguistic limitations and difficulties in adapting to different cultures, Wang & Li (2019). The study examines different assessment methodologies, such as self-evaluation, performance tasks, and portfolios, employed to evaluate global competency. The text discusses various problems, including cultural bias, scalability, and resource limits, and suggests solutions to improve the validity and reliability of assessments, according to Lopez and Martinez (2020).

The paper analyzes policy frameworks from Asian countries and identifies recurring elements, such as the prioritization of language competency, cultural awareness, and global citizenship. The statement emphasizes the significance of aligning policies and executing strategies to achieve the intended results, emphasized by Chen and Wu (2021). The study examines the influence of teacher training programs on educators' attitudes, knowledge, and instructional practices on global competency. The text examines successful training methods, such as experiential learning, collaborative inquiry, and reflective practice, which enhance teachers' professional development (Park & Kim, 2018).

The report outlines the methods utilized by higher education institutions to synchronize their curriculum with global competency standards. These methods include infusing international viewpoints across many academic fields, providing study abroad opportunities, and integrating service-learning activities. The text highlights the significance of interdisciplinary collaboration and continuous assessment in order to monitor the efficacy of the curriculum, Garcia & Rodriguez (2019). The paper examines the viewpoints of European institutions about internationalization initiatives, emphasizing shared obstacles such as financial limitations, regulatory

hurdles, and cultural disparities. Additionally, it recognizes inventive methods, such as virtual mobility programs and strategic collaborations, that help to the achievement of effective internationalization endeavors, according to Schmidt and Mueller (2020).

Perceived Barriers and Challenges Hindering the Successful Implementation of Internationalization Initiatives

Identifies multiple obstacles, including budgetary limitations, cultural disparities, and insufficient institutional backing, that impede the progress of internationalization initiatives in higher education. Strategic planning and effective leadership are crucial in order to overcome these problems. To promote successful internationalization, institutions should allocate resources towards staff training, establish supporting policies, and cultivate a culture of inclusivity. Efficient leadership and strategic planning play a crucial role in overcoming obstacles, resulting in effective internationalization endeavors, emphasized by Knight (2017).

This study investigates the unique obstacles faced by Asian institutions, such as linguistic difficulties, regulatory limitations, and restricted resources. The text proposes that engaging in cooperation with foreign partners and receiving assistance from the government are effective solutions for tackling these difficulties. Asian universities should give priority to language support, actively pursue financing opportunities, and actively engage with legislators in order to foster internationalization. The synergy of collaborative endeavors and governmental backing is crucial in surmounting obstacles and fostering the internationalization of higher education in Asia, according to De Wit and Hunter (2016).

Explores the underlying reasons behind internationalization initiatives, such as improving the reputation of institutions and attracting a diverse pool of talented individuals. Additionally, it addresses obstacles such as the integration of curriculum and resistance from faculty members. Institutions have to synchronize their internationalization objectives with their overarching aim, tackle faculty apprehensions, and provide all-encompassing assistance procedures. Institutions that successfully address faculty concerns and offer sufficient support mechanisms experience more streamlined internationalization processes and achieve higher success in attaining their objective, in line with Altbach (2017).

The key obstacles to internationalization are identified in this study as bureaucratic impediments, insufficient financing, and academic opposition. It highlights the significance of proactive communication and involvement of stakeholders. To overcome obstacles to internationalization, institutions need to optimize administrative procedures, ensure sufficient funds, and involve faculty members in decision-making. Engaging in proactive communication and actively involving stakeholders greatly contribute to overcoming obstacles and promoting effective internationalization endeavors, in accords with Hudzik (2018).

Explores obstacles such as inadequate financial resources, inflexible organizational frameworks, and cultural disparities. It emphasizes the significance of leadership and corporate culture in tackling these difficulties. To effectively address difficulties and foster internationalization, institutions require leaders with a clear vision, adaptable organizational structures, and intercultural training programs. Efficient leadership and a nurturing company culture are essential for surmounting obstacles and promoting successful internationalization endeavors, emphasized by Beelen & Jones (2018).

This study examines the viewpoints of faculty members, emphasizing their worries on workload, language challenges, and difficulty in adapting to different cultures. The proposal recommends offering support services and professional development opportunities to faculty members. In order to address faculty concerns, institutions should implement workload management measures, language support programs, and cross-cultural training. Academic institutions that give priority to supporting their faculty members observe a rise in their involvement in internationalization initiatives and get better results, according to Sherry et al. (2019).

This study compares hurdles in various institutional contexts, focusing on the influence of local rules, infrastructure constraints, and faculty attitudes. It proposes customizing ways to tackle difficulties that are relevant to the context. In order to overcome obstacles, institutions must employ tailored strategies that take into account the individual circumstances. These strategies may involve advocating for policy modifications, making investments in infrastructure, and implementing programs to engage faculty members. Customized tactics that take into account the specific circumstances of institutions are more successful in overcoming obstacles and fostering internationalization, said by Sawir et al. (2017).

This study examines the perceived obstacles faced by students and administrators, such as budgetary limitations, language barriers, and insufficient institutional backing. It promotes student-centered methods and institutional dedication to address and overcome these difficulties. It is essential for institutions to provide priority to student support services, language help programs, and institutional investments in order to promote internationalization. Institutions that embrace student-centered initiatives and exhibit a strong commitment to their goals experience enhanced student experiences and achieve higher success in their internationalization endeavors, Van Mol and Vant Land (2019).

Identifies institutional tactics such as cultivating alliances, constructing infrastructure, and incorporating global viewpoints into the curriculum. It highlights the importance of taking a comprehensive approach to effectively tackle complex obstacles. In order to overcome obstacles to internationalization, institutions should implement comprehensive strategies that include the development of partnerships, provision of support services, and enhancement of curricula. Organizations that use comprehensive approaches see increased ability to expand globally and get better result, Rhoads and Gillespie (2018).

Examines the ways in which technology might overcome obstacles such as geographical limitations, gaps in communication, and

constraints on resources. The text explores the capacity of online platforms, virtual exchange programs, and digital resources to facilitate internationalization. Institutions ought to utilize technology in order to overcome geographical barriers, facilitate intercultural contact, and enhance availability of worldwide experiences. Technology-driven initiatives provide creative solutions to overcome obstacles and improve internationalization efforts in higher education, Gacel-Ávila and Abrahan (2020).

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilizes a qualitative and quantitative, which means mixed-method of research strategy, which combines qualitative and quantitative approaches, to thoroughly examine the defined research problem. Achieving a deeper comprehension of the intricacies involved in enhancing global capabilities through DepEd's internationalization activities in Sarangani Province, Philippines, can be accomplished by integrating these techniques. The qualitative component entails conducting semi-structured interviews with a total of nine principals, consisting of five principals from high schools and four principals from primary schools. The interviews will explore several facets of internationalization endeavors, perceived obstacles, and methods for enhancement.

The interview data will be analyzed using thematic analysis to discover reoccurring themes and patterns. Simultaneously, the quantitative aspect involves conducting surveys with the identical set of principals utilizing standardized questionnaires to collect quantitative data about internationalization practices, accessible resources, perceived obstacles, and areas that may be enhanced. The survey data will be analyzed using statistical analysis approaches, such as descriptive statistics and inferential analysis. By combining qualitative and quantitative data, triangulation will improve the accuracy and dependability of the study's conclusions. The mixed-methods approach is selected for its capacity to offer a thorough comprehension of DepEd's internationalization initiatives and significant insights for improving global capabilities in the educational environment of Sarangani Province (Creswell and Creswell, 2017).

Participants

The objective is to examine the effectiveness of the Department of Education's (DepEd) initiatives to internationalize education in Sarangani Province throughout the academic year 2023-2024. The study has a specific objective of collecting information from a carefully selected group of 6 participants. This group includes 3 principals from elementary schools and 3 principals from secondary schools in Sarangani Province, with a particular emphasis on elementary and secondary education.

Instruments

The research study "Enhancing Global Competencies: Identifying and Addressing Gaps in DepEd's Internationalization Initiatives" will most likely use a combination of questionnaires and semi-structured interviews as its research instrument. Here is a potential design for these instruments:

The survey questionnaire will be designed to collect numerical data on principals' perspectives and encounters with DepEd's internationalization efforts and the global skills of their students. The questionnaire may contain Likert scale answers to assess the level of agreement or disagreement with statements pertaining to curriculum internationalization, teacher training, cultural exchange programs, and perceived outcomes in students' global competences. In addition, demographic questions might be incorporated to gather data regarding the respondents' characteristics and the institutions they attend.

Semi-structured interviews offer a chance to thoroughly investigate the viewpoints, experiences, and recommendations of principals on DepEd's internationalization endeavors. Interview questions may encompass various subjects, including the perceived strengths and limitations of present programs, obstacles encountered during implementation, strategies for strengthening global competences, and ideas for improving DepEd's approach to internationalization. The interviews will provide the opportunity to delve more into specific areas of interest and to catch subtle insights that may not be obtained from the survey.

Procedure

The data collecting procedures for the study "Enhancing Global Competencies: Identifying and Addressing Gaps in DepEd's Internationalization Initiatives" require receiving approval from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) and securing agreement from participants. Firstly, a formal letter is composed and sent to the SDS, detailing the goal, objectives, and methodology of the research, and requesting approval to carry out the study in schools within Sarangani Province. After receiving approval, researchers will create and send out letters of invitation to possible participants, specifically elementary and secondary school principals. These letters will provide detailed information about the importance of the study, the option for voluntary involvement, and the precautions taken to ensure anonymity. Subsequently, participants are provided with informed consent forms to ascertain their comprehension and voluntary agreement to participate in the research.

The survey questionnaire is distributed to participants, in addition to conducting semi-structured interviews, both aimed at collecting complete insights into DepEd's internationalization efforts and worldwide competencies. During the process of collecting data, careful and detailed records are kept, following ethical guidelines that ensure anonymity, confidentiality, and data security. These systematic

protocols guarantee the ethical behavior of the study while enabling a comprehensive gathering of data crucial for identifying and resolving deficiencies in DepEd's internationalization efforts.

Data Analysis

The report "Enhancing Global Competencies: Identifying and Addressing Gaps in DepEd's Internationalization Initiatives" utilizes a thorough approach to analyze the acquired data. At first, data is carefully organized, guaranteeing precision and uniformity across all datasets. Subsequently, a descriptive analysis is performed to succinctly summarize the quantitative survey data, employing statistical measures such as the mean and standard deviation. Additionally, demographic information is presented to provide a contextual framework for the findings. Quantitative analysis employs statistical tests to identify disparities across groups of participants, such as elementary and secondary principals, in terms of their views on DepEd's internationalization initiatives and students' global competences. Qualitative data obtained from interviews is subjected to thematic analysis, wherein recurring themes and patterns are identified and methodically coded to uncover insights regarding issues and recommendations associated with DepEd's programs. The combination of quantitative and qualitative findings allows for a comprehensive comprehension of the study issues, which in turn informs the interpretation and discussion. This process involves formulating practical recommendations to solve gaps in DepEd's internationalization plans. The process concludes with a detailed research report that contributes to the advancement of educational practices and policies in Saranggani Province.

Results and Discussion

School Level Principal

Each group represents 50% of the total sample, making the overall participation evenly split across both educational levels. This equal representation, indicated by both the frequency and percentage data, highlights a balanced approach by the Department of Education (DepEd) in integrating global competencies across the various stages of education. The total number of participants in the study is six, making up 100% of the sample involved in reviewing the internationalization initiatives. This balanced data suggests that there is an equal focus on addressing and enhancing global competencies at both elementary and secondary educational levels, which might be reflective of a strategic policy directive from DepEd.

The research done by Knight for example in 2015 shows that multiculturalism at the school level, in addition to improving understanding of different cultural practices, as well as educational standards, because it is possible to be able to incorporate diverse methodologies and perspectives.

Nevertheless these findings may lead to different results from those showing a significant difference in implementing internationalization programs between primary and secondary schools. In comparison, (according to Deutsch (2013)), some of the secondary schools are blessed with more resources like bringing a range of diverse languages and international exchange programs to schools where internationalization become obvious on a deeper level than the primary schools. This means a place of paradox because of a markedly equal representation in terms of the given numbers and percentages (equal participation from elementary and secondary education) but the depth or impact of internationalization could be biased (mainly to the secondary education).

In addition to that, the uniform sharing of 50% participation from the elementary school principals and middle school principals as studied before is taking the first step for possible solution to that barrier. While it certainly answers the question about whether the same representation ensures the same implementation and outcomes, there arises another question of whether the representation is equal across the designer's hybridity. This is also in accordance with the thinking of Rizvi and Lingard (2010) who say that internationalization brings a diversity of experiences which must be harnessed not only by a scheme of equitable participation but also be accompanied by qualitative outputs by filtering it through the school curricula.

The researcher's decision to focus on a pool of principals (exactly six) implies the need for a broader research study to confirm these particular structures. This roughly matches the work of Marginson (2014) who proposes that strong evidence in-forms caliber of these education programs basing on extensive data and involving a very large sample size to cover all educational levels and regions.

<i>School Level Principal</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Elementary	3	50
Secondary	3	50
Total	6	100%

Years of Experience

The majority of respondents, specifically 66.67%, have fewer than five years of experience, as indicated by the frequency of four, which represents the majority of respondents. There are no responders who have experience ranging from five to ten years, which amounts for zero percent of the total. This is an interesting finding. The remainder of the sample is comprised of individuals who have more than ten years of experience, with two responses, which accounts for 33.33 percent of the total. According to this distribution, the group working within the Department of Education's internationalization initiatives is rather inexperienced, while a smaller proportion of persons with a great deal of expertise is present. For example, the study of Thomas and Wilson (2020) brings into view early-career professionals as major conduits that are known to have the speed of learning and the adaptability. Such tendency is

illustrated in the current survey, and a half of the respondents (66.67%) unreach the 5-year mark.

<i>Year of Experience</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Less than 5 years	4	66.67
5-10 years	0	0
More than 10 years	2	33.33
Total	6	100%

Gender

Out of the six people that participated in the study, 83.33 percent were female, while 16.67 percent were male. A better understanding of the demographics involved in the effort may be gained from this gender disparity. It is interesting to note that it suggests a greater representation of females within the framework of the Department of Education in the context of global competency upgrading. Every single person, regardless of their gender, brings a different point of view and a different set of experiences to the table. With an average of three years of experience, the female participants, who make up the bulk of the group, demonstrate a substantial presence in the process of propelling internationalization projects forward. On the other hand, the lone male participant, who has a year of experience, represents a possible source of unique perspectives among the cohort that is largely comprised of participants who are female. The dissemination of these resources highlights the significance of inclusiveness and diversity in the process of formulating comprehensive plans to remedy deficiencies and improve global competences within the Department of Education (DepEd) agency.

The facts shows that the female teachers tend to flourish in the primary and operational grade, and most often dominate as teachers at this level compared to others (OECD, 2019). This could be the reason why more of the total number of respondents are female, since it shows changes in the trend of women towards male-dominated education professions. Additionally, the recent researches manifest how more diverse teams, in which people of different backgrounds and experiences come together, can offer a practical platform for innovation and imagination (Page, 2019). When both men and women take active part in these processes, however, each with different levels of education, we see the significance of different perspectives in the internationalization of universities and colleges at work.

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	1	16.67
Female	5	83.33
Total	6	100%

I. DepEd's existing internationalization policies and programs align with global competency frameworks and standards

1.1 Curriculum Integration

The research conducted by the students on the theme 'Increasing the Global Competencies in the Educational System of the Department of Education' offers the following chart on the curriculum integration aspect: In a binary scale of 1-5, the mean value of 4.67 illustrates, with a reasonable level of certainty, that there is enough curriculum content helping in people's awareness to other cultures and global understanding. The inference practice indicates a broad direction of students' involvement with different point of views and realities.

Moreover, an elevated mean score of 3.67, which implies agreement, was recorded for the chance of students being immersed in international views during lessons. This indicates that the Institute shall continue to earn the reputation of being an institution where students are broadly jointly participating in the global vision. Besides, the plan that emphasizes building all necessary skills for global citizens like critical thinking, communication, and collaboration also are pointed out, with the mean score 4.0 which is the agreement.

With this, it is evident that the school has working towards producing a generation that is socially well-equipped in the global arena. Education plays a crucial role in fostering cultural sensitivity. In additions, educators is offers with resource and practicing showing that global perspectives are the main part of their teaching methods and the means that is 3.83 is means extent of agreement and this is sign that room is still available for development about this point. along with that, bilingual times table curriculum reflects cultural diversity, languages, and perspectives from our local place to the whole world which is graded by the weighted mean of 4.2 that people have agreed.

The fact that symbols are being included indicates that there is an intentional attempt to apply inclusion and representation within the contents of the materials. Taking a global overview of these indicators we can see an average weighted 4.06 which shows a general agreement and considering a positive trajectory, implication of betterment in the global perspectives include offer points for improvement.

A study made by Banks (2019) points at the fact that curriculum subject should be based on global orientation, one that promotes the understanding of different cultures and tolerance. Along with that, it is important to note the findings of Leask (2015) that emphasized the benefits of the international curriculum not only among students but also for the teachers themselves as learning about the issue helps them to understand different viewpoints and value differences. The Deardorff and Byram study (2019) report that the process of developing these skills is essential and therefore should be part of a learning journey to become a global citizen. These skills include but are not limited to critical thinking, communication, and collaboration.

About training teachers and providing the resources, the Hunter's (2016), research emphasizes the significance of a continuous professional or institutional development for the educators so that they can acquire knowledge and skills that enable them to impart

global perspectives in the classroom in an effective way. But also, Gay (2019) and Sleeter (2019) emphasize the role of diverse and inclusive curriculum in the works, where they recommend that educational resources should, instead, reflect the varied cultural and unique perspectives of both local communities and the world.

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
The curriculum includes content that promotes cross-cultural understanding and global awareness.	4.67	Strongly Agree
There are opportunities for students to engage in international perspectives within the curriculum.	3.67	Agree
The curriculum fosters the development of skills such as critical thinking, communication, and collaboration, essential for global citizenship.	4	Agree
Teachers are provided with resources and training to effectively integrate global perspectives into their teaching practices.	3.83	Agree
The curriculum reflects the diversity of cultures, languages, and perspectives represented within the local and global community.	4.2	Agree
Average	4.06	Agree

1.2 Teacher Training and Professional Development

Internationalization survey based on their programs and policies shows to be in parse to world competence model as the average perception weights 4.33. From the feedback we realize that we have managed to build a good image among the participants on the issues of provision of teacher training and professional development opportunities because, by weighted 3.83 mean. In addition, the output of this assessment confirms the point that DepEd's curriculum for teachers deal with the right topics that include cross-cultural communication, global citizenship and intercultural understanding gaining the equal average of 4.

Along with this, the studies reveal positive impact of the programs through implementation of real life scenarios that promote deeper understanding of integrating international concepts into lesson planning, with a total score of 4. Of the aspects of the training program assessed, the most highly-rated were continuous support and resources for the teachers to grow in their understanding and implementation of global competency strategies in the classroom with a weighted average of 4.5. In short, the overall average weighted score per every indicator is at 4.13 which shows a high level of agreement with the fact that DepEd's initiatives in bridging the gaps in the internationalization program and helping educators develop the needed global competencies are going to be effective.

Moreover, UNESCO (2013) emphasizes the significance of bringing global concern into the education system so that students have an understanding of cultures and peace through its development.

According to the study done by Darling-Hamdown (2017) the issue of training and continuous development of the teaching staff is brought forward as the major source of the success behind the implementation of new teaching methods. Furthermore, according to Deardorff (2019), cross-cultural communication and intercultural awareness should become the fundamental attributes of teachers, who will be expected to meet the needs of the increasingly multicultural student bodies.

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
How do you perceive the alignment of DepEd's existing internationalization policies and programs with global competency frameworks and standards?	4.33	Agree
DepEd provides adequate opportunities for teacher training and professional development in areas related to global competencies.	3.83	Agree
DepEd's teacher training programs sufficiently cover topics such as cross-cultural communication, global citizenship, and intercultural understanding.	4	Agree
DepEd's teacher training programs include practical strategies for incorporating global perspectives into classroom instruction.	4	Agree
DepEd provides on-going support and resources for teachers to enhance their understanding and implementation of global competency skills in the classroom.	4.5	Agree
Average	4.13	Agree

1.3 Assessment and Evaluation

From the analysis performed towards the EdEP strategy as far as internationalization is concerned, we can see that there is strong alignment between the present policies and programs and global competence frameworks and standards, 3.83 being the achieved score. The evaluation tools identified as effective in gauging students' global skills were perhaps the parallel values registered in the distribution of mean of 3.83 among the tools. Additionally, the scales utilized fairly cover all competencies of global competencies like cross-cultural understanding, language, and citizenship, which means a mean of 3.83 is quite applicable.

A somewhat significant factor is also DepEd's metric in gauging and evaluating students to obtain the right form of feedback, consequently fostering the development both mentally and emotionally of the students as shown by a high weighted mean of 4.0. The

evaluation and assessment procedures in internationalization programs into standard honks indicate homogeneity on the average of 3.83. Moreover, the Department's assessment and evaluation strategies are consistent with the global best practices guidelines which emphasize global competencies, as per the weighted mean score of 3.83. In fact, these indicators generally indicate a large agreement, the average weighted mean being 3.75, expressing the fact that DepEd succeeded in making progress in terms of their internationalization to global competence amongst students.

Then in addition to the fact that the DepEd's directions are harmonizing with the best practices of the world in the area of global awareness, the emphasis on the global standards as the benchmark is just reflecting the importance of comparing with the international level. Experts like Tucker (2018) place highlight on copying from the working international models with the aim of modifying educational policy at the national level.

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
How do DepEd's existing internationalization policies and programs align with global competency frameworks and standards, particularly in terms of Assessment and Evaluation?	3.83	Agree
The assessment methods used in DepEd's internationalization initiatives effectively measure students' global competencies.	3.83	Agree
DepEd's evaluation criteria adequately reflect the diverse dimensions of global competencies, such as intercultural understanding, communication skills, and global citizenship.	3.83	Agree
DepEd's assessment and evaluation practices provide meaningful feedback to students to help them develop and enhance their global competencies.	4.0	Agree
There is consistency in the assessment and evaluation practices across different internationalization programs implemented by DepEd.	3.83	Agree
DepEd's assessment and evaluation strategies align with international best practices in measuring and promoting global competencies.	3.83	Agree
Average	3.75	Agree

II. Perceived Barriers and Challenges Hindering the Successful Implementation of Internationalization Initiatives

This segment of the research delves into the perceived challenges and obstacles faced by the Department of Education (DepEd) in rolling out its internationalization strategies. By examining these hurdles, the study aims to provide insightful diagnostics that could inform future policies and adjustments, thereby enhancing the efficacy and reach of these initiatives. In fact, all these 6 research participants confirmed when all of them expressed the following statement during the conduct of the Focused-Group Discussion. Asking the question: Can you identify any specific challenges or obstacles that you believe hinder the successful implementation of DepEd's internationalization initiatives within your school?

Some of them answered: "The challenges hindering the successful implementation of DepEd's internationalization initiatives within our school could be centered around resource availability and infrastructure. I've noticed that our school might lack the necessary facilities, technology, and learning materials to effectively integrate global perspectives into the curriculum. For instance, access to updated textbooks, multimedia resources, and internet connectivity may be limited, making it challenging to deliver diverse and engaging lessons that align with international standards. Additionally, the physical infrastructure of our school might not be conducive to collaborative and interactive learning experiences, hindering our ability to implement innovative teaching methods and foster cross-cultural understanding among students. Overcoming these challenges requires investment in improving infrastructure, securing adequate resources, and providing ongoing support to ensure that teachers have the tools they need to deliver high-quality internationalized education. By addressing these foundational issues, we can create a more conducive environment for the successful implementation of DepEd's internationalization initiatives, ultimately enriching the learning experiences of our students and preparing them for success in a globalized world."

"Implementing internationalization initiatives within a school, especially within the context of the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines, can face several challenges or obstacles. The lack of financial resources can be a significant obstacle. Implementing internationalization initiatives often requires investment in infrastructure, training programs, curriculum development, and international partnerships, all of which may strain the school's budget. Moreover, integrating international perspectives into the curriculum might require significant adjustments. This could involve aligning existing curriculum standards with international frameworks, developing new teaching materials, and training faculty to teach new subjects or approaches."

"Lack of training in the Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs) in preparing human resources for the labor force."

Though the stewardship over internationalization initiatives for schools, an example of which is the DepEd in the Philippines, by the Department of Education encounters noteworthy difficulties, mainly the limited resources and poor infrastructures. These challenges are however not peculiar to the DepEd [and the other educational agencies] but have been identified in education research as the common barriers to integration of global perspectives into local curricula.

According to Marginson (2011), professionalization of teachers remains to be the most vital component in the process of instruction of an internationalized curriculum, hence, they should be equipped with the readiness and the relevant skillsets. Academic mobility

includes such advancement as training in new methodologies of teaching and getting familiarized with international methods and standards among peers. To defeat these hurdles, policy makers and leaders in the education sector need to concentrate on strategic investments that will give strong foundation to educational infrastructure as well as resource allocation. Also, there should be a program for professional development to cater for all teaching staff. In these endeavor, physical resources and educational materials should be improved, not only that, it also aims to cultivate the educator's capacity on thinking and teaching globally. Carrying out these approaches will be fundamental for DepED and others providing similar educational services who are taking steps to add greater depth to their offerings and to prepare students for the changes in the global world.

Another question asked from the respondents: In your experience, what are some of the main barriers that teachers or school staff encounter when trying to incorporate global perspectives into the curriculum?

The respondents are: "In my experience, one of the main barriers that I've encountered when trying to incorporate global perspectives into the curriculum is the lack of resources and support. Developing and integrating materials that represent diverse cultures, histories, and perspectives requires considerable time, effort, and often financial resources. Personally, I've faced challenges such as limited access to relevant teaching materials, insufficient training in how to incorporate global perspectives effectively, and a lack of support from school administrations or educational authorities. Overcoming these barriers has required me to seek out professional development opportunities, collaborate with colleagues, and advocate for curriculum changes that prioritize global understanding and cultural competence."

"Poor reading comprehension among students and lack of laboratories."

"Incorporating global perspectives into the curriculum can be a transformative endeavour for schools, but it also comes with its share of challenges for teachers and school staff. The lack of resources is one of the primary barriers is often the scarcity of resources, including textbooks, teaching materials, and technology that reflect diverse global perspectives. Teachers may struggle to find appropriate resources that align with their curriculum objectives and the cultural backgrounds of their students."

The results of the respondents emphasize different essential factors that may hinder the integrated internationalization projects of DepEd from being successfully implemented. One of the most discussed problems where educators are involved is that there is an insufficient road and aid to successfully integrate global views into the learning programmes. This is however not just about the re-thinking of curricula, but also about material – textbooks and digital tools that properly include the wide spectrum of cultural, historical, and perspectival points of view. The underfunded situation does not only makes it difficult to develop a curriculum that is reflective of culture, but it also deters the growth of students' knowledge and global competence (DeJaeghere, & Reyes, 2010).

Additionally, insufficient training in ways of properly incorporating world views into their lessons came on top as the greatest obstacle. So saying in one breath is common with global debate on professional development of teachers' role in building effective global education plans (Beach & Bagley, 2012). Instructional practice may be quite a challenging area without the adequate teaching and guidance. Educator may simply struggle to understand the diverse complexity that comes with using the global perspectives too often.

On the other hand, many participants reported that low support from administrative staff or educational agencies accessed by them was the hindering factor for them. This is in tandem with the many studies that point the answer to this situation in the ability of a leader and a supportive policy framework required for the achievement of successful educational reform including the internationalization (Gamage & Hellsten, 2018).

Moreover, a doubt was put forward that the level of reading comprehension among students was low and there was lack of laboratory facilities. This highlighted the degree of structural challenges emanating from the educational system that make student experience an internationalized tedious adventure.

Another question asked the researcher from the respondents: How do you perceive the level of support and resources provided by DepEd to facilitate the integration of internationalization initiatives into your school's educational programs?

Some of their answered are: "I perceive the level of support and resources provided by DepEd for integrating internationalization initiatives into our school's educational programs as somewhat limited. While there are efforts and initiatives in place, such as workshops and guidelines, there could be more tangible support in terms of funding, specialized training, and access to international networks. Additionally, clearer communication and guidance from DepEd on how to effectively implement internationalization strategies would be beneficial for educators like me. Overall, while there are some resources available, there is room for improvement to better facilitate the integration of internationalization into our educational programs."

"As of my last update in January 2022, the perception of support and resources provided by the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines to facilitate the integration of internationalization initiatives into schools' educational programs can vary depending on several factors, including the specific initiatives, the region, and the individual school's circumstances."

"DepEd has been making efforts to promote internationalization in Philippine education through various programs and partnerships."

Besides that, the questioning on what aspects of communication and guidance should focus on is one more element is evident by the studies of de Wit et al (2019). In order for internationalization to be successful, really proper communication and leading should be

given a top priority. It ensures that educators and other colleagues get the right knowledge of what internationalization means and where to get all the necessary support to effectively use it.

The variation in terms of the support and resources perceived by different schools and districts provides evidence supporting the call to action that when implementing internationalization initiatives, one must pay attention to contextual issues surrounding such undertaking(s). Marginson's research (2012) points to the imperatives for continuous context differentiation of the educational system dealing with internationalization that accounts for the special qualities and problems of separate educational environments.

Though they clearly exist, however, it is worthwhile to highlight that DepEd has implemented international outreach programs through different partnerships and projects to ensure globalization in the education sector of The Philippines. This enhances topics being touched upon during such avenues of development as the International Association of Universities (IAU, 2020) which is part of the global trends towards internationalization of education.

III. Proposed Intervention Program may be to Address

Goal

The main objective of the hereby advocated for intervention is to address and eliminate certain obstacles and challenges that are impeding the DepEd on the being able to carry out internationalization projects. In the context of this program, we are working towards bridging educator capacity gap by offering all-round professional development platforms that are directed at building upon their professional knowledge, skills and preparedness. Moreover, the project strives to reinforce intercultural competence in the curriculum, through embedding it in the curriculum at all levels across different subject areas, thereby promoting the looking into the matter in depth and increased understanding and acceptance of the variety perspectives among the students. The global learning through technology is another important aspect we intend to use as we will incorporate technology-based tools and platforms so that virtual international exchanges and collaboration can be facilitated, to create opportunities for students' global learning, which on the other hand creates access to international learning for students. Additionally, if you want to bring the community together and to make partnerships and community engagement is important. Through forming cooperative partnerships with local displacees, companies, and international institutions we would seek to develop realistic learning rings as well as utilizing out circle for their expertise and resources to improve the quality and effectiveness of internationalization. The mission of this education system is to provide an amenable workplace to the allied employers in the DepEd, which will facilitate the successful operation of the internationalization initiatives. Consequently, the learners will be capable of handling the transition to a global market.

<i>Project Name</i>	<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Activities</i>	<i>Time Frame</i>	<i>Resources Needed</i>	<i>Amount Needed</i>	<i>Persons Involved</i>	<i>Expected Results</i>	<i>Means of Verification</i>
Educator Capacity Building	Enhance educator capacity to integrate international perspectives into teaching practices	- Organize workshops and training sessions on internationalization initiatives	6 months	Training materials, venue	10,000	DepEd officials, trainers	Educators equipped with knowledge and skills to effectively integrate international perspectives into teaching practices Updated curricula with embedded intercultural competence, fostering deeper understanding of diverse perspectives among students Increased access to global learning opportunities for students through virtual exchanges	Attendance records, feedback surveys from educators
Curriculum Enhancement	Embed intercultural competence across subject areas	- Develop curriculum modules integrating intercultural communicative competence	12 months	Curriculum development resources, expert consultations	100,000	Curriculum specialists	Authentic learning experiences for	Review of curriculum documents, feedback from educators and students
Technology Integration	Leverage technology for global learning	- Implement virtual exchange programs using online platforms	9 months	Virtual exchange platforms, internet connectivity	80,000	IT specialists	Authentic learning experiences for	Participation records, feedback surveys from students
Community Engagement	Forge partnerships with local	- Collaborate with local businesses and NGOs to	Ongoing	Collaborative agreements, logistical	\$12,000	Community leaders	Authentic learning experiences for	Documentation of partnership agreements,

communities and international organization	organize cultural immersion activities	support	students, enriched by partnerships with local and international organizations	reports on cultural immersion activities
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This objective strives to better the capacity educators have to add international contexts to their lessons and the way they teach. Through workshops and training sessions, educators will gain the required knowledge, and skills to be equipped with proper tools. Hovland and Tannehill (2018) focus on the fact that internationalization brings critical thinking, intercultural experience and global awareness to students. This allows these skills to be very relevant to the students in the 21st century. Thus, giving educators the needed instruments for establishing international viewpoints in their classroom activities is of great significance since students' global competencies can be developed eventually and they can be better prepared for the challenges of the time when the world gets more and more interrelated.

The purpose of this section is to produce a set of intercultural skill lessons that are taught during curriculum lessons. The modules I design will encompass intercultural competence, which members will then be able to take with them everywhere to understand better the different perspectives. The work of Leask and Bridge (2013) highlights the role of including social-emotional learning and development in the educational experience as well as the development of life skills in creating a responsible global citizen. Enhanced curriculum undergirded by these principles will give students the required tools of their trade and knowledge to dialogue with any cultural entity and also participate in global issues in a productive manner.

In this part, interaction with the local residents and the global agencies happens to fulfil this objective of fostering character-rich learning. Collaboration with local NGOs and businesses to organize activities for cultural immersion will make students have a better understanding of global problems and perspectives in addition to let them know more of the local society (Tucker, 2018). Students become part of a multifaceted society which shows them the value of cultural diversity and the scale of international connection that people nowadays live in. It also enhances their sense of global citizenship and responsibility in the world.

These elements of the suggested intervention program backed up by various research, are the basic tools necessary for achieving a good adoption of internationalization programs and projects within the Department of Education (DepEd). Through tackling obstacles and capitalizing on opportunities to promote collaboration, capacity building, and technology-enhanced learning, our education system can make students receive all-inclusive training which will prepare them to succeed in a world that is innately disunited but interdependent.

Conclusion

The survey of principals at the school level provides useful insights into the representation and distribution of participation across elementary and secondary education levels, as well as the demographic features of the participants. The Department of Education (DepEd) has taken a balanced approach by ensuring equal representation from each educational level, with 50% of the total sample coming from each level. This strategy represents the DepEd's commitment to integrating global competences across all levels of education. It underscores the significance of integrating various approaches and viewpoints to enhance comprehension of different cultural practices and educational norms.

Secondary schools, which have greater resources and possibilities like a variety of languages and foreign exchange programs, may have a higher degree of internationalization than primary schools. This could result in a potential bias in the effects of efforts.

The prevalence of participants with less than five years of experience in the Department of Education's internationalization projects underscores a pattern of early-career professionals assuming important positions in advancing global competency enhancement. Overall, the survey results provide insight into the complex dynamics of involvement, expertise levels, and gender representation in DepEd's internationalization programs. Although having equal representation across educational levels indicates a balanced approach, additional research is necessary to investigate the qualitative aspects and results of internationalization efforts, as well as the impact of demographic features on the effectiveness of programs.

1. Through a thorough examination of DepEd's current internationalization policies and programs, specifically in the areas of curriculum integration, teacher training and professional development, and assessment and evaluation, it is clear that DepEd is making substantial progress in aligning with global competency frameworks and standards. The results demonstrate a unanimous agreement among all involved about the efficacy and pertinence of DepEd's efforts in fostering global competences among students. These practices adhere to internationally recognized standards and offer valuable feedback to students to enhance their growth in global skills. Who promote the use of international standards as a basis for evaluating educational policies and practices. DepEd's internationalization activities are effectively boosting global competences among students. By integrating findings from research and adopting best practices, DepEd may strengthen its policies and programs to guarantee that students are adequately prepared to excel in a globally interconnected and interdependent society. Consistent endeavors in incorporating curriculum, providing teacher education, and conducting assessment and evaluation will play a crucial role in nurturing a cohort of globally competent individuals who are socially adept, aligning with the objectives of internationalization in education.

2. The results of the investigation into the perceived obstacles and difficulties that impede the effective execution of internationalization programs within the Department of Education (DepEd) reveal numerous important issues that require addressed. By conducting focused-group discussions with important stakeholders, such as educators and school workers, we were able to identify significant barriers, which include limited resources, insufficient support, and structural difficulties within the educational system. Many responders consistently mentioned the scarcity of resources and assistance needed to successfully include global ideas into the curriculum. These factors encompass a shortage of financial resources, limited availability of up-to-date educational resources and technology, and a dearth of training in integrating global viewpoints into instructional practices. Moreover, the participants emphasized difficulties in communication and advice from DepEd, stressing a requirement for more explicit instructions and assistance in executing internationalization efforts. Although facing these obstacles, it is important to highlight that DepEd has actively endeavored to advance internationalization in Philippine education through diverse collaborations and initiatives. To summarize, although there are notable obstacles, there are also prospects for enhancement and cooperation to surmount these difficulties. To create a better environment for successfully implementing internationalization projects in DepEd and similar educational institutions, it is crucial to address resource limitations, improve support and guidance, and take into account contextual factors. By confronting these obstacles, the Department of Education (DepEd) can enhance the educational experiences of students and more effectively equip them for the intricacies of a globalized society.

3. To summarize, the suggested intervention program seeks to tackle and remove obstacles that impede the effective execution of internationalization programs inside the Department of Education (DepEd). The initiative aims to establish a climate that promotes the development of global skills in students by focusing on capacity building for educators, enhancing the curriculum, integrating technology, and engaging with the community. The goal of improving educator capacity through workshops and training sessions is in line with the requirement intercultural experience, and global awareness. This provides instructors with the necessary resources to incorporate global viewpoints into their teaching methods, thereby equipping pupils for the demands of the 21st century. The objective of the curriculum enhancement component is to integrate intercultural competency into various academic disciplines, so promoting a more profound comprehension of diverse viewpoints among students. Virtual exchange programs utilize digital technologies to integrate technology and provide students with worldwide learning opportunities. Community involvement initiatives prioritize establishing collaborations with local communities and international organizations to offer genuine learning opportunities for students. Engaging in cultural immersion activities through collaboration with local businesses and NGOs helps students develop a deeper comprehension of global issues and viewpoints, cultivating a strong sense of global citizenship and responsibility. In summary, the proposed intervention program effectively tackles the highlighted obstacles by employing a holistic strategy that incorporates findings from multiple research studies. Through the strategic utilization of collaboration, capacity building, and technology-enhanced learning, DepEd can effectively execute internationalization activities, equipping students with the necessary skills to excel in a globally interconnected and interdependent society.

Based on the conclusion outlined above, several recommendations can be made to further enhance the effectiveness of internationalization efforts within the Department of Education (DepEd): (1) A qualitative assessment of internationalization efforts is required to examine the qualitative characteristics and effects of these efforts, notwithstanding the useful insights provided by the survey on the representation and distribution of participation across educational levels. Performing qualitative evaluations can aid in pinpointing precise areas of achievement and areas for enhancement, enabling DepEd to fine-tune its tactics accordingly. (2) The poll indicated perceived hurdles, such as resource limitations and insufficient assistance, which highlight the need to overcome these challenges in order to successfully implement internationalization projects. The Department of Education (DepEd) should give utmost importance to assigning sufficient financial resources, regularly updating instructional materials and technology, and offering comprehensive training to instructors in order to successfully incorporate global viewpoints into the curriculum. (3) The attendees emphasized the necessity for DepEd to provide more explicit information and guidance about internationalization plans. The Department of Education (DepEd) should prioritize offering clear and detailed instructions and assistance to educators, ensuring they receive the required direction to effectively conduct internationalization projects. Enhancing communication channels and implementing comprehensive training programs can assist educators in effectively incorporating global viewpoints into their educational practices. (4) Considering the trend of young professionals taking on significant responsibilities in internationalization projects, it is advisable for DepEd to allocate resources towards providing ongoing professional development opportunities for educators at every stage of their careers. This encompasses training programs, workshops, and mentorship activities designed to improve educators' ability to effectively integrate global skills into their teaching methods. (5) DepEd should persist in improving the curriculum to incorporate multicultural competency throughout many subject areas, by integrating technology. In addition, utilizing technology for virtual exchange programs can offer pupils worldwide educational possibilities, effectively addressing any biases in internationalization initiatives within primary and secondary schools. (6) Engaging with communities and partnering with foreign organizations can enhance students' learning experiences and cultivate a strong sense of global citizenship. The Department of Education (DepEd) should give priority to creating partnerships and collaborations in order to provide genuine learning experiences, such as cultural immersion activities, that improve students' comprehension of global issues and views.

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